

Impact of Sampling Frequency on the Performance of DEVIN: A Personal EM UL Exposimeter

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Abstract

DEVIN is a miniaturized personal electromagnetic (EM) exposimeter that allows recording powers emitted by the mobile phone as well as identifying the user activities along the day. It is simply a hardware integrated into the shell of the smartphone. In the context of epidemiological studies, DEVIN is required to collect data from volunteers over a long period of time, e.g., a week. This implies a critical challenge related to the autonomy of its battery, which should be charged once per day. One solution to extend the battery autonomy consists on decreasing the sampling frequency. Therefore we intend in the present work to evaluate the performance of DEVIN at two different sampling frequencies for two various signals types, i.e., voice over LTE (VoLTE) and data uploading signals.

1 Introduction

The total number of global mobile subscribers will grow from 66% of population in 2018 to over 70% of the global population by 2023, according to [1]. The second fastest growing mobile device category is smartphones, after the machine to machine (M2M) [1]. Despite this tremendous evolvment, smartphones have been identified among the principal contributors to the radio-frequency electromagnetic field (RF-EMF) exposure [2]. This implies the necessity to monitor RF-EMF exposure of the general population, in particular the Up-Link (UL) one, which is still predominant compared to the Down-Link exposure.

EMF exposure is characterized through various measurement equipment, as reviewed in [3]. In particular, the UL exposure could be assessed using mobile middleware chipset based logging tools, such as the drive test solutions which are suitable for spot measurement campaigns [4]. On the other hand, in the context of epidemiological studies, the EMF exposure of the population in the daily life could be assessed through dedicated software applications installed on the volunteer's mobile phone, e.g., XMobiSense [5]. However such applications rely on the operating system version and require continuous updates. This is resolved with EM coupling hardware-based solutions, such as DEVIN [6, 7] which ensures full autonomy from the mobile OS versioning and enables long term evolution exposure monitoring. The user can keep his habits and usage for the entire day. No additional application is running on the mobile which can maintain its usual power consumption.

DEVIN is a miniaturized personal UL EM exposimeter

Figure 1. The personal UL EM exposimeter DEVIN.

[6, 7]. It consists on a EM near field probe, a RR power acquisition plus some sensors, all integrated into the shell of the smartphone, as shown in Figure 1. Due to proximity sensors and accelerometers, DEVIN is able to identify the mobile phone usage or, in other words, the relative position of the source with respect to the human body. Moreover, it allows recording, at certain sampling frequency (f_s), the real powers emitted (TX) by the phone at both the cellular and WiFi frequency bands. Since DEVIN provides an assessment of the UL exposure from daily usages of smartphones, the challenge is to maintain its 600 mAh battery operational during all the day. Indeed, the battery autonomy could be extended by decreasing the sampling frequency f_s . Therefore, we intend in the present work to evaluate the performance of DEVIN, in terms of data accuracy, for two different sampling frequencies. To this end, we consider two different types of signals, i.e., a very dense signal (data uploading) and a relatively low dense signal (voice over LTE or VoLTE).

2 Overview of DEVIN

DEVIN is an add-on module attached on the smartphone cover. It is composed of two RF chains dedicated for measuring TX powers in six cellular frequency bands as well as in two WiFi bands, resulting in eight frequency bands sequentially in time. Each chain consists on a probe with parallel RF bandpass filters, one RF root mean square (RMS) power detector, and an analog to digital converter (ADC). The DEVIN probe is just coupling -20 dB (1%) from Tx power flowing through the mobile's antenna port. We note that this does not affect the radio link quality, neither the UL power control, nor the mobile specific absorption rate (SAR) value. However, the EM coupling between the mobile antenna and the DEVIN RF probe must be calibrated for each of the eight frequency bands and ideally for each

Figure 2. Time variation of two UL signals with different densities: (a) VoLTE call, (b) 18 MB video file measured with an spectrum and signal analyzer R&S FSVA.

model of mobile phone. In practice, the calibration consists in evaluating the transfer function between the output value from the DEVIN ADC divided by the RF power transmitted from the mobile [7].

The RMS UL TX power and the distance are measured with up to 1 KHz sampling frequency, time-stamped, and collected in a 16 GB SD memory card. The acquisition strategy can be reconfigured to measure one or all the bands quasi-simultaneously. At the end of a recording period, the raw ADC data are transferred from the DEVIN SD card to a PC through USB link, the calibration table is applied, and data are analyzed offline.

3 Methodology

We aim to assess the impact of the sampling frequency f_s on the performance of DEVIN, e.g., if all the emitted signals are well detected and with an accurate average power value. To this end, we consider two different sampling frequencies, i.e., $f_s = 10$ Hz and $f_s = 100$ Hz, which provide a battery autonomy of almost 11 and 6 hours, respectively. Furthermore, we consider two various types of signals that differ in their density regarding time (i.e., the percentage of power values that are above the noise level): 19% for a VoLTE call signal and 95% for a 18 MB video file uploaded signal. These signals are respectively shown in Figure 2 (a) and (b).

The experimental validation of DEVIN consists on the following steps:

Figure 3. Setup of the experimental validation of DEVIN.

Signal acquisition: First, we identify the active frequency band over which the mobile phone is operating in order to configure the spectrum analyzer. Then, we use a classical mobile to emit two UL signals by performing a VoLTE call and uploading an 18 MB video file to a server. In the same time, these signals are acquired using a spectrum analyzer R&S FSVA in zero span mode via a dedicated antenna placed close to the mobile phone. The length of the recorded signal is limited to 5 s with 20 MHz bandwidth. The time variation of these signals is shown in Figure 2. While the data uploading signal is very dense even though with frequent returns to the noise level, the VoLTE signal is represented by periodic discontinuous events corresponding to approximately 20 ms of duty cycle [8]. It is important to note that this duty cycle changes with respect to the percentage of voice activity.

Re-playing signals and recording with DEVIN: The aforementioned acquired signals are saved and then re-played alternatively and repetitively with a signal generator R&S SMBV100B, connected to an antenna. We used also a spectrum analyzer in order to visualize the signals. The measurement setup is shown in Figure 3. After setting up the DEVIN sampling frequency to either $f_s = 10$ Hz or $f_s = 100$ Hz, we turned on DEVIN in its logging mode and put it under the antenna. We note that this experiment was repeated for each value of f_s .

Data post-processing: The DEVIN logged raw data are then calibrated in order to obtain TX powers in dBm. The values below the noise plus 3 dB are filtered out, and the average power values are computed over 0.5 s. These averages over different f_s values are then compared to the reference signals recorded by the spectrum analyzer.

4 Results

We note that all the average values are computed over 0.5 s. We first compare the reference signal, also averaged over

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Comparison of average values of reference signal vs. DEVIN's data at 10 Hz and 100 Hz: (a) DataUL, (b) VoLTE.

0.5 s window, to the average values computed over the data recorded with DEVIN at both $f_s = 10$ Hz and $f_s = 100$ Hz, for both uploaded video and VoLTE call. The results, shown in Figure 4, reveal a good agreement for the video signal since it is a dense signal. Regarding the VoLTE signal, the comparison with DEVIN at $f_s = 100$ Hz shows a fair agreement on average, however we note that the shape of the average signal can change from one record to another one due to the low density nature of such scarce signal and also to the different synchronization between the DEVIN and the real signal (Figure 5 (b)). In this specific case, the average metric may present a bias which is not happened over dense signals.

Figure 5 presents the comparison between the data from DEVIN (in dBm) and their average values. The results show that at high sampling frequency ($f_s = 100$ Hz) the Devin is always able to detect all the signals, however with $f_s = 10$ Hz, it is not able to detect low density signals as the case of 5 s duration VoLTE. Notice that from EMF exposure point of view, the contribution of such signals is very

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Validation of data detection with DEVIN: (a) $f_s = 100$ Hz, (b) $f_s = 10$ Hz.

low. Moreover, VoLTE calls last in general for time duration much longer than 5 s. Therefore, we perform VoLTE calls with several duration and we record with DEVIN at $f_s = 10$ Hz. The results, reported in Figure 6, show that VoLTE calls with duration higher than 30 s are always well detected. Moreover, we note that the duty cycle of the calls is not constant and depends on the voice activity. As depicted in the figure, there is a long VoLTE call, which is very dense. The Devin succeeds to assess the transmitted power profile with $f_s = 10$ Hz.

5 Conclusion

The present work presents some experiments to evaluate the performance of a personal UL EM exposimeter called DEVIN. Two different types of signals were considered, i.e., a VoLTE of low density and a file data uploading with high density. DEVIN is used to log TX powers at two different sampling frequencies, $f_s = 10$ Hz and $f_s = 100$ Hz. The results show that DEVIN is always able to detect and give an accurate average TX power values for very dense signals, even with a low value of f_s . On the other hand, sig-

Figure 6. Logging VoLTE calls by DEVIN with $f_s = 10$ Hz.

nals with low density require higher sampling frequency or longer lasting duration in order to be detected, such as the VoLTE. We note that the signal density changes even for a given type of signal (e.g., VoLTE), according to several parameters. The averaged values over a given duration (here 0.5 s) should be considered with care since the ratio between this average and maximum values change regarding the density of the emitted signal. Future works will consider new metrics to embrace both the variability in time and in power level over longer period like the whole day.

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